

Logic Vector Version 8

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1 Introduction

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(\frac{\forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z)}{\Delta} \right), \\
 & \left(\frac{\leftrightarrow \exists y \in U: f(y) = x}{\Delta}, \frac{\leftrightarrow \exists s \in S: x = T(s)}{\Delta}, \frac{\leftrightarrow x \in f \circ g}{\Delta} \right), \\
 & \left(\frac{V \rightarrow U}{\Delta}, \frac{\sum_{f \subset g} f(g)}{\Delta}, \frac{\sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h}{\Delta} \right), \\
 & \left(\frac{f_{PQ}(x) - f_{RS}(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{f_{TU}(x) - f_{RS}(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{f_{PQ}(x) - f_{TU}(x)}{\Delta} \right), \\
 & \left(\frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1} a_1 + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2} a_2 + \dots + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_n} a_n \right) \\
 & \left(\frac{\phi(\mathbf{x}) \leq \psi(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta}, \frac{\phi(\mathbf{x}) \geq \psi(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta}, \frac{\phi(\mathbf{x}) = \psi(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta} \right) \\
 & \left(\frac{\neg \chi(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta}, \frac{\chi(\mathbf{x}) \theta(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall y \in X, \chi(y) \iff \theta(y)}{\Delta} \right). \\
 & \left(\frac{\exists z \in N, \phi(z) \wedge \psi(z)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall w \in N, \chi(w) \theta(w)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists x \in N, \phi(x) \vee \psi(x)}{\Delta} \right). \\
 & \left(\frac{\exists u \in N, \alpha(u) \vee \beta(u)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall v \in N, \gamma(v) \rightarrow \delta(v)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall y \in N, \epsilon(y) \iff \zeta(y)}{\Delta} \right). \\
 & \left(\frac{\exists m \in N, \lambda(m) \mu(m)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall n \in N, \kappa(n) \vee \iota(n)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall x \in N, \eta(x) \nu(x)}{\Delta} \right). \\
 & \left(\frac{\exists a \in N, \pi(a) \rho(a)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall b \in N, \sigma(b) \wedge \tau(b)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists c \in N, \xi(c) \leftrightarrow \theta(c)}{\Delta} \right). \\
 & \left(\frac{\exists d \in N, \nu(d) \varphi(d)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall e \in N, \omega(e) \vee \psi(e)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists f \in N, \chi(f) \rightarrow \eta(f)}{\Delta} \right). \\
 & \left(\frac{\exists p \in N, \kappa(p) \lambda(p)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall q \in N, \mu(q) \nu(q)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall r \in N, \xi(r) \leftrightarrow \iota(r)}{\Delta} \right). \\
 & \left(\frac{\exists g \in N, \tau(g) \upsilon(g)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall h \in N, \varphi(h) \wedge \omega(h)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists i \in N, \psi(i) \vee \chi(i)}{\Delta} \right). \\
 & \left(\frac{\exists j \in N, \eta(j) \leftrightarrow \kappa(j)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall k \in N, \lambda(k) \mu(k)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists l \in N, \nu(l) \rightarrow \xi(l)}{\Delta} \right). \\
 & \left(\frac{\forall a \in N, \iota(a) \iff \tau(a)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists b \in N, \upsilon(b) \vee \varphi(b)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall c \in N, \omega(c) \rightarrow \psi(c)}{\Delta} \right). \\
 & \left(\frac{\exists d \in N, \chi(d) \eta(d)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall e \in N, \kappa(e) \lambda(e)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists f \in N, \mu(f) \leftrightarrow \nu(f)}{\Delta} \right). \\
 & \left(\frac{\exists g \in N, \xi(g) \iota(g)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall h \in N, \tau(h) \wedge \upsilon(h)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists i \in N, \varphi(i) \vee \omega(i)}{\Delta} \right). \\
 & \left(\frac{\exists j \in N, \psi(j) \chi(j)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall k \in N, \eta(k) \leftrightarrow \kappa(k)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall l \in N, \lambda(l) \rightarrow \mu(l)}{\Delta} \right). \\
 & \left(\frac{\neg(\exists x \in N) \rightarrow \forall y \in N}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in N, (\forall y \in N) \exists s \in S}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists y \in N, \forall y \in N, (\forall y \in N) (\exists y \in N)}{\Delta} \right),
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\frac{\forall y \in N, (\exists y \in N)(\forall y \in N)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in N, (\forall z \in N) \rightarrow (\exists z \in N)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists z \in N, (\forall z \in N) \vee (\exists z \in N)}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\neg(\exists z \in N)(\exists z \in N)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists x \in N, (\exists x \in N)(\exists x \in N)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall t \in N, \exists x \in N(\exists x \in N)}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\neg(\forall y \in N) \vee (\forall y \in N)}{\Delta} \iff \frac{\forall y \in N}{\Delta}, \frac{(\forall y \in N)(\forall y \in N) \rightarrow \exists y \in N}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists y \in N, (\forall y \in N) \iff \forall y \in N \exists y \in N}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\forall z \in N, \exists z \in N \forall z \in N}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists z \in N, (\forall z \in N) \rightarrow \forall z \in N}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists z \in N, (\forall z \in N) \leftrightarrow \exists z \in N}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\neg(\exists z \in N) \leftrightarrow \forall z \in N}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists x \in N, (\exists x \in N) \leftrightarrow \exists x \in N}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall t \in N, \exists x \in N \vee (\exists x \in N)}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\neg(\exists x \in U) \exists x \in U}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall y \in U, (\forall y \in U) \forall y \in U}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in U, (\exists z \in U) \leftrightarrow \forall z \in U}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\forall y \in U, (\exists y \in U) \vee \forall y \in U}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in U, \exists z \in U (\forall z \in U)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists z \in U, (\forall z \in U) \exists z \in U}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\exists x \in N, \forall y \in U \rightarrow (\forall x \in N)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall y \in U, \exists z \in U (\neg \exists x \in N)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists z \in U, (\forall z \in U) \wedge \forall z \in U (\exists z \in U)}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\exists x \in U, \forall y \in U \iff \forall x \in U}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists y \in U, (\exists y \in U) \rightarrow \exists y \in U}{\Delta}, \frac{(\forall x \in U) \rightarrow \exists x \in U \wedge (\forall y \in U)}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\neg(\forall x \in U) \exists x \in U}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall y \in U, \exists z \in U \leftrightarrow (\exists z \in U)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists z \in U, (\exists z \in U) \rightarrow \forall z \in U}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\exists a \in U, \neg \exists b \in U}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall c \in U, \exists d \in U}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall e \in U, \neg \exists f \in U \forall g \in U}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\exists h \in U, (\exists i \in U)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall j \in U, \forall k \in U \vee \forall l \in U}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists m \in U, (\forall n \in U \vee \forall o \in U)}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\forall p \in U, \exists q \in U \vee \forall r \in U}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists s \in U, (\forall t \in U)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists u \in U, \neg \forall v \in U}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\exists a \in N, (\exists a \in N)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall b \in N, \forall b \in N}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists c \in N, (\forall c \in N)}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\forall d \in N, \exists e \in N \vee \forall f \in N}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall d \in N, (\exists d \in N)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall h \in N, \forall h \in N}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\forall i \in N, \forall j \in N \exists k \in N}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall l \in N, \exists m \in N}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall n \in N, (\neg \forall r \in N) \vee \exists o \in N}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\exists p \in N, (\forall q \in N \wedge \forall r \in N)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall s \in N, \forall t \in N \rightarrow \exists u \in N}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall v \in N, (\neg \exists w \in N) \wedge (\forall x \in N)}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\neg \exists a \in \forall y \in U: \exists s \in S}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall h \in \forall y \in U: \forall z \in N}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists h \in \forall z \in N: \exists z \in U}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\forall x \in \exists y \in N, \exists z \in \exists u \in \exists v \in}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists t \in \forall y \in U, \forall z \in N, \forall u \in \forall v \in}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists d \in \forall a \in \forall b \in \forall c \in \forall e \in U}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\forall f \in \forall g \in \forall h \in \forall i \in \forall j \in P}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists k \in \exists l \in \exists m \in \exists n \in P, \forall o \in}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists p \in \exists q \in \exists r \in P, \exists s \in \forall t \in Q}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\neg \exists b \in \exists c \in P, \exists d \in \exists e \in \exists f \in R \iff \forall y \in \mathbf{R}^2}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists g \in \forall h \in \forall i \in R, \forall j \in \forall k \in \mathbf{R}^2}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists l \in \forall m \in R, \forall n \in \forall o \in \mathbf{R}^2, \forall p \in \mathbf{R}^3}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\neg \exists q \in R, \exists r \in \exists s \in \mathbf{R}^2, \exists t \in \mathbf{R}^3, \exists u \in \mathbf{R}^4}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall v \in \forall w \in \mathbf{R}^2, \forall x \in \mathbf{R}^3, \forall y \in \mathbf{R}^4, \exists z \in \mathbf{R}^n}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall a \in \mathbf{R}^2, \forall b \in \mathbf{R}^3, \forall c \in \mathbf{R}^4, \forall d \in \mathbf{R}^n, \forall f \in \mathbf{R}^m}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{(\exists a \in X, \forall y \in Y)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in X, (\forall y \in Y)}{\Delta}, \frac{(\neg \exists z \in X, \forall y \in Y)}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\forall z \in X, \exists y \in Y, \neg \exists a \in X}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists b \in X, \forall y \in Y, \exists b \in X}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg \exists c \in X, \exists b \in X, \forall y \in Y}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{(\exists y \in Y, \exists a \in X)}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg \forall y \in Y, \exists y \in Y, \exists a \in X}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg \exists b \in X, \forall y \in Y, \exists a \in X}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\exists y \in Y, \exists a \in X, \neg \exists b \in X}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg \exists c \in X, \exists d \in Y, \exists a \in X}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg \exists e \in Y, \exists a \in X, \neg \exists c \in X}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\exists y \in P, \forall y \in Q}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in P, \exists z \in Q}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg \forall z \in P, \forall z \in Q}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\exists y \in Q, \forall y \in P, \neg \exists z \in Z}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in Z, \exists z \in P, \neg \exists a \in Q}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall a \in Q, \forall b \in P, \neg \exists c \in Z}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\forall a \in Q, \exists a \in P, \neg \exists z \in P}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists y \in Z, \forall y \in Q, \neg \exists z \in P}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg \exists z \in P, \exists z \in Z, \forall y \in Q}{\Delta} \right),
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\frac{\forall a \in Z, \exists b \in P, \neg \exists y \in Q}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall y \in P, \exists b \in Z, \neg \exists x \in Q}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg \exists c \in Q, \forall z \in Z, \exists z \in P}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\neg \exists y \in Q, \exists y \in P, \forall y \in Q}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists a \in P, \forall z \in P, \forall z \in Q}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg \forall z \in Z, \neg \exists z \in P, \forall b \in Q}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\forall a \in Q, \exists y \in Z, \neg \exists z \in Q}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg \exists z \in Q, \exists z \in P, \neg \exists z \in Z}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists y \in Q, \exists y \in P, \exists y \in Q}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{(\exists y \in Y, \forall y \in \Delta)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in Y, (\forall y \in \Delta)}{\Delta}, \frac{(\neg \exists z \in Y, \forall y \in \Delta)}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\exists y \in \Delta, \forall y \in Y, \neg \exists z \in Y}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in Y, \exists z \in \Delta, \neg \exists a \in Y}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall a \in Y, \forall b \in \Delta, \neg \exists c \in Y}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\exists a \in \Delta, \forall y \in Y, \neg \exists z \in \Delta}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists y \in Y, \forall z \in \Delta, \neg \exists z \in \Delta}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg \exists z \in \Delta, \exists z \in Y, \forall b \in Y}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\forall a \in Y, \exists y \in \Delta, \neg \exists y \in Y}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg \exists z \in Y, \exists z \in \Delta, \neg \exists z \in Y}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg \exists y \in Y, \exists y \in \Delta, \exists y \in Y}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\forall y \in Y, \exists y \in \Delta, \neg \exists z \in \Delta}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in \Delta, \neg \exists z \in \Delta, \neg \exists z \in Y}{\Delta}, \frac{\neg \exists z \in Y, \forall x \in \Delta, \neg \exists z \in \Delta}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\neg \exists a \in \Delta, \forall y \in Y, \neg \exists z \in Y}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall x \in \Delta, \forall y \in Y, \neg \exists z \in \Delta}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists y \in Y, \exists y \in \Delta, \exists y \in Y}{\Delta} \right), \\
& \left(\frac{\forall x \in \Delta, \exists y \in Y, \neg \forall z \in \Delta}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in Y, \neg \exists z \in Y, \neg \forall z \in \Delta}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists y \in Y, \forall y \in \Delta, \forall y \in Y}{\Delta} \right).
\end{aligned}$$